

Effect of titanium-based supports on the electrochemical activity and stability of iridium nanoparticle catalysts for OER in PEM water electrolyzer

Lucinda Blanco-Redondo^a, Yevheniia Lobko^{*a}, Alina Madalina Darabut^a, Jaroslava Nováková^a, Thu Ngan Dinhová^a, Maryna Vorokhta^b, Miquel Gamón Rogríguez^a, Milan Dopita^c, Michal Mazur^d, Jakub Hraníček^e, Yurii Yakovlev^a, Tomáš Hrbek^a, Vladimír Matolín^a, Iva Matolínová^a.

^aDepartment of Surface and Plasma Science, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Charles University, V Holešovičkách 2, 180 00, Prague 8, Czech Republic. E-mail: yevheniia.lobko@mff.cuni.cz

^bInstitute of Rock Structure and Mechanics, Geochemistry Department, The Czech Academy of Science, V Holešovičkách 94, 182 09, Prague 8, Czech Republic.

^cDepartment of Condensed Matter Physics, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Charles University, Ke Karlovu 5, 121 16, Prague 2, Czech Republic.

^dDepartment of Physical and Macromolecular Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Hlavova 8, 128 00, Prague 2, Czech Republic.

^eDepartment of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Hlavova 2030/8, 128 00, Prague 2, Czech Republic.

Fig. S1 EDX spectra of the supports and the Ir-supported nanoparticles.

Tab. S1 EDX atomic ratios for the bare support and Ir-supported catalysts in powder form.

Powder	Ir/Ti	Ti/O	Ti/C	Ti/N
TiO ₂	-	0.50	9.70	-
Ir/TiO ₂	0.08	0.50	1.70	-
TiC	-	3.30	0.60	-
Ir/TiC	0.08	3.10	0.90	-
TiN	-	2.60	10.80	0.84
Ir/TiN	0.07	2.00	3.50	0.85

Fig. S2 TEM micrographs of the Ti-based supports TiO_2 (a), TiC (b), and TiN (c), and their corresponding particle size distribution (d-f).

Fig. S3 STEM micrographs of the Ir/TiO_2 nanoparticles at different magnifications taken with bright-field annular detector (ABF) (a-b) and HAADF detector (c).

TEM micrographs at higher magnification are shown in **Fig. S4**, permitting the crystallinity structure of the Ir nanoparticles to be recognized. In addition,

line intensity profiles analysis (**Fig. S4a-c**) shows a distance between parallel planes of about 2.3 Å and 1.9 Å for Ir, which correlates with the d-spacing of the (111) and (200) planes, respectively.

Fig. S4 TEM micrographs of the Ir supported on TiO₂ (a), TiC (b), and TiN (c), and the line intensity profiles of Ir nanoparticles.

The SAXS patterns in **Fig. S5** correspond to the bare supports. However, the bigger particle size and the wider particle size distribution made the data fitting difficult, and it was not done.

Fig. S5 SAXS patterns of TiO₂, TiC, and TiN.

Fig. S6 TEM images of TiO₂ (a), TiC (b), and TiN (c).

Fig. S7 Hydrogen underpotential deposition peak for Ir/TiO₂, Ir/TiC, Ir/TiN, and Ir black.

The electrical conductivity of the support nanoparticles, TiO₂, TiC, and TiN, was calculated from the reciprocal of the electrical resistivity. The methodology followed for the measurements is the same one used and reported previously at work [1]. Briefly, the electrical resistivity is related to the electrical resistance by Ohm's law (see Eq. S1). Experimentally, the electrical resistance was measured by using the four-point probes (for low resistance) and two-point probes (for high resistance) methods using an SP-150-1 potentiostat (BioLogic Science Instruments).

$$\rho = \frac{V}{I} \frac{A}{s} \quad (\text{S1})$$

where A is the cross-section of the sample, and s is the space between probes.

Tab. S2 Resistance, resistivity, and conductivity of the bare support nanoparticles: TiO₂, TiC, and TiN.

Sample	Resistance [Ω]	Resistivity [Ω cm]	Conductivity [S cm ⁻¹]
TiO ₂	1.41 · 10 ⁸	2.09 · 10 ⁸	5.75 · 10 ⁻⁹
TiC	0.05	0.02	54.30
TiN	1.93	0.30	3.37

Fig. S8 Cyclic Voltammetry of TiO₂ (a), TiC (b), and TiN (c) from cycles 1 to 20 in acidic electrolyte (0.5 M H₂SO₄), scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹, and potential range 0.051 to 1.56 V_{RHE}.

The charge of the redox peaks shown in **Fig. S9** was calculated by integrating the area under the peaks, which appear in the potential range between 0.6 and 1.3 V vs. RHE, with double-layer charge subtraction. The inserts in **Fig. S9** show the peak areas magnified and coloured for cycles 2 (orange), 5 (yellow), 10 (green), 15 (pink), and 20 (purple).

Fig. S9 Redox peaks for cycles 2, 5, 10, 15, and 20 for Ir/TiO₂ (a), Ir/TiC (b), Ir/TiN (c), and Ir black (d). In the inserts, peak areas appear magnified and coloured.

Fig. S10 Mass activity review of Ir nanoparticles supported on TiO₂, TiC, and TiN nanoparticles. Details of the references can be found in **Tab. S3**. The higher the MA is, the better the catalyst.

Tab. S3 Comparison of the electrochemical parameters of supported Ir nanoparticles in ex-situ testing by Rotating Disk Electrode.

Catalyst	Ir/WE [mg cm ⁻²]	j [mA cm ⁻²] @1.525V _{RHE}	ΔE _{10 mA cm⁻²} [mV]	MA [A g _{Ir} ⁻¹] @1.525V _{RHE}	Tafel slope [mV dec ⁻¹]	Electrolyte	Scan rate [mV s ⁻¹]	In-situ test	Ref.
Ir/TiO ₂	0.040	52.7 @1.525V _{RHE}	260	1298 @1.525V _{RHE}	47.7	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	5	Yes	This work
Ir/TiC	0.039	45.9 @1.525V _{RHE}	259	1173 @1.525V _{RHE}	51	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	5	Yes	This work
Ir/TiN	0.036	4.8 @1.525V _{RHE}	329	133 @1.525V _{RHE}	79	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	5	Yes	This work
Ir black	0.203	51.5 @1.525V _{RHE}	253	252 @1.525V _{RHE}	50.5	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	5	Yes	This work
IrTiO _x -350	0.65	9.0 @1.525V _{RHE}	296	13.8 @1.525V _{RHE}	64.0	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	5	No	[2]
IrO _x /Ti ₄ O ₇ (3:7)	0.01	~4.5 @1.525V _{RHE}	325	302 @1.55V _{RHE}	46	0.1 M HClO ₄	5	Yes	[3]
IrO ₂ -blueTiO ₂	0.28	~12.0 @1.58V _{RHE}	342	1380 @1.58V _{RHE}	68.2	0.1 M HClO ₄	5	No	[4]

Tab. S4 Continued

Catalyst	Ir/WE [mg cm ⁻²]	j [mA cm ⁻²]	$\Delta E_{10 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}}$ [mV]	MA [A g _r ⁻¹]	Tafel slope [mV dec ⁻¹]	Electrolyte	Scan rate [mV s ⁻¹]	In-situ test	Ref.
IrO ₂ 50wt%@TiO ₂	0.010	-	-	51 @1.525V _{RHE}	-	0.1 M HClO ₄	-	Yes *	[5]
IrO ₂ /TiO ₂ Umicore	0.05	-	-	47 @1.55V _{RHE}	-	0.1 M HClO ₄	-	Yes *	[5]
Ir _{30wt%} /TiO _x	-	8.18 @1.60V _{RHE}	-	158.3 @1.6V _{RHE}	-	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	6	No	[6]
IrOOH _x 30%/TiO ₂ 375°C	0.76	-	200	62@ 1.53V _{RHE}	-	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	20	Yes *	[7]
Ir/TiC	0.040	-	-	~25 @1.48V _{RHE}	74	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	0.167	No	[8]
Ir _{20wt%} /TiC	0.056	780 @1.74V _{RHE}	-	-	-	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	50	No	[9]
Ir _{20wt%} /TiC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Yes *	[10]
Pt-Ir _{40wt%} /TiC	0.11	120 @1.74V _{RHE}	-	-	-	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	50	No	[11]
Ir _{33wt%} /TiC	0.048	~7.0 @1.75V _{RHE}	~330	150 @ 1.55V _{RHE}	53	0.1 M HClO ₄	10	No	[12]
Ir _{thin film} /TiC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Yes *	[13]
IrO ₂ 15wt%@Ir/TiN	0.057	6.5 @1.525V _{RHE}	324	162.7 @1.55V _{RHE}	64.7	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	5	No	[14]
TiN/IrO ₂ -31	0.225	~4.0 @1.525V _{RHE}	313	~200.0 @1.55V _{RHE}	65.5	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	10	No	[15]
IrO _x /TiN	0.040	~9.0 @1.525V _{RHE}	293	270.8 @1.54V _{RHE}	40.8	0.1 M HClO ₄	10	Yes *	[16]
IrO ₂ @Ir _{40wt%} /TiN	0.04	-	232	637 @1.65V _{RHE}	63.3	0.1 M HClO ₄	10	No	[17]
Ir/TiON _x -P25	0.013	-	234	96.39 @1.525V _{RHE}	71	0.1 M HClO ₄	20	No	[18]
Ir NPs	0.028	-	~326	~100 @1.50V _{RHE}	-	0.1 M HClO ₄	10	No	[19]
Ir black	0.379	12.0 @1.525V _{RHE}	284	65.0 @1.55V _{RHE}	61.8	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	5	No	[14]
IrO ₂ Alfa Aesar	0.010	-	-	279 @1.55V _{RHE}	-	0.1 M HClO ₄	-	Yes *	[5]

*See Tab. S7 for the measurement details and results of the water electrolyzer test.

~ Value read from a plot in the article.

- No determination, calculation, or specification is made in the article.

Fig. S11 Tafel plot and linear fitting for Ir/TiO₂ (red), Ir/TiC (orange), Ir/TiN (blue), and Ir black (grey).

Fig. S12 Linear Sweep Voltammetry from cycles 1 to 5 for Ir/TiO₂ (a), Ir/TiC (b), Ir/TiN (c), and Ir black (d), and magnification of the LSV at the potential range at which the current density of 10 mA cm⁻² is reached (inserts).

Tab. S5 Overpotential at 10 mA cm⁻² over the cycles.

	Overpotential (mV) at 10 mA cm ⁻²				
	Cycle 1	2	3	4	5
Ir/TiO₂	260	262	264	266	266
Ir/TiC	259	284	304	347	
Ir/TiN	329				
Ir black	253	262	264	266	266

Tab. S6 Mass activity at 1.525 V_{RHE} over the cycles.

	MA (A g _{Ir} ⁻¹) at a potential 1.525 V				
	Cycle 1	2	3	4	5
Ir/TiO₂	1298	961	833	763	684
Ir/TiC	1173	377	200	72	11
Ir/TiN	133	25	16	-	-
Ir black	252	191	177	158	157

Tab. S7 Comparison of the electrochemical parameters of supported Ir nanoparticles in in-situ testing by single-cell PEM water electrolyzer.

Catalyst	Membrane thickness [μm]	Ir loading on the support [wt%]	Ir loading on MEA [mg cm ⁻²]	Cell temperature [°C]	Cell voltage @ 1 A cm ⁻²	Ref.
Ir/TiO ₂	50.8 (N212)	19.9	0.3	80	1.56	This work
Ir/TiC	50.8 (N212)	19.2	0.3	80	1.85	This work
Ir/TiN	50.8 (N212)	17.9	0.3	80	X	This work
Ir black	50.8 (N212)	-	0.3	80	1.61	This work
IrO _x /Ti ₄ O ₇ (7:3)	125 (N115)	76	0.9	80	1.54	[3]
IrO _x unsupported	125 (N115)	-	1.1	80	1.52	[3]
IrO ₂ @TiO ₂	50.8 (N212)	40	0.4	80	1.67	[5]
IrO ₂ /TiO ₂ Umicore	50.8 (N212)	75	0.5	80	1.72	[5]
Ir/TiC	88 (N1135)	20	0.3	80	1.90	[10]
Ir commercial	88 (N1135)	-	1.5	80	1.70	[10]

Tab. S8 Continued

Catalyst	Membrane thickness [μm]	Ir loading on the support [wt%]	Ir loading on MEA [mg cm^{-2}]	Cell temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	Cell voltage @ 1 A cm^{-2}	Ref.
Ir _{thin film} /TiC	125 (N115)	70.6	0.24	80	1.71	[13]
IrO _x /TiN	50.8 (N212)	30	0.2	60	1.69	[16]
IrOOH _x /TiO ₂ 375 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	50.8 (N212)	45	0.34	80	1.61	[7]
IrOOH _x /TiO ₂ 365 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	50.8 (N212)	30	0.24	80	1.71	[7]
IrO ₂ /TiO ₂ Umicore	50.8 (N212)	75	1.25	80	1.60	[7]

Fig. S13 Chronoamperometry results for Ir/TiO₂, Ir/TiC, Ir/TiN, and Ir black measured at the voltage switching between 1.6 V and 1.7 V (5 min long steps, 3 h total duration, 3 repetitions: CA 1, CA 2, and CA 3).

Fig. S14 PEIS measurements at different potentials for Ir/TiO₂ (a-c), Ir/TiC (d-f), Ir/TiN (g-i), and Ir black (j-l). The measurements were repeated three times, including loop 1 (a, d, g, and j), loop 2 (b, e, h, and k), and loop 3 (c, f, i, and l). Experimental data are shown as dots; fitted curves are shown as red lines.

Fig. S15 Randles Equivalent Electrical Circuit for both anodic and cathodic contributions applied to Ir/TiC (a), and solely anodic contribution applied to Ir/TiO₂, Ir/TiN, and Ir black (b).

Fig. S17 EDX spectra of MEAs cross section after testing in the PEM water electrolyzer.

Fig. S16 Parameters extracted from PEIS fitting for Ir/TiO₂, Ir/TiC, Ir/TiN, and Ir black: (a) ohmic resistance (R), (b–d) charge transfer resistance, (e–g) constant phase element (CPE, Q), (h–j) CPE exponent (α).

Fig. S18 EDX mapping of MEAs cross section after testing in the PEM water electrolyzer. Colour code: light blue (titanium), dark blue (fluor), pink (iridium).

References

- [1] Darabut AM, Lobko Y, Yakovlev Y, Rodríguez MG, Veltruská K, Šmíd B, et al. Influence of thermal treatment on the structure and electrical conductivity of thermally expanded graphite. *Advanced Powder Technology* 2022;33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appt.2022.103884>.
- [2] Lin Y, Wu B, Chen A, Su J, Chen L. Iridium-titanium oxides for efficient oxygen evolution reaction in acidic media. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2023;48:10368–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.11.348>.
- [3] Cha JI, Baik C, Lee SW, Pak C. Improved utilization of IrO_x on Ti₄O₇ supports in membrane electrode assembly for polymer electrolyte membrane water electrolyzer. *Catal Today* 2022;403:19–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2022.01.015>.
- [4] Nguyen CTK, Tran NQ, Le TA, Lee H. Covalently bonded Ir(IV) on conducted blue TiO₂ for efficient electrocatalytic oxygen evolution reaction in acid media. *Catalysts* 2021;11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal11101176>.
- [5] Pham C Van, Bühler M, Knöppel J, Bierling M, Seeberger D, Escalera-López D, et al. IrO₂ coated TiO₂ core-shell microparticles advance performance of low loading proton exchange membrane water electrolyzers. *Appl Catal B* 2020;269:118762. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2020.118762>.
- [6] Bernsmeier D, Bernicke M, Schmack R, Sachse R, Paul B, Bergmann A, et al. Oxygen evolution catalysts based on Ir–Ti mixed oxides with templated mesopore structure: impact of Ir on activity and conductivity. *ChemSusChem* 2018;11:2367–74. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201800932>.

- [7] Böhm D, Beetz M, Gebauer C, Bernt M, Schröter J, Kornherr M, et al. Highly conductive titania supported iridium oxide nanoparticles with low overall iridium density as OER catalyst for large-scale PEM electrolysis. *Appl Mater Today* 2021;24:101134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmt.2021.101134>.
- [8] Karimi F, Peppley BA. Metal carbide and oxide supports for iridium-based oxygen evolution reaction electrocatalysts for polymer-electrolyte-membrane water electrolysis. *Electrochim Acta* 2017;246:654–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2017.06.048>.
- [9] Ma L, Sui S, Zhai Y. Preparation and characterization of Ir/TiC catalyst for oxygen evolution. *J Power Sources* 2008;177:470–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2007.11.106>.
- [10] Ma L, Sui S, Zhai Y. Investigation on high performance proton exchange membrane water electrolyzer. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2009:678–84.
- [11] Fuentes RE, Colón-Mercado HR, Martínez-Rodríguez MJ. Pt-Ir/TiC electrocatalysts for PEM fuel cell/electrolyzer process. *J Electrochem Soc* 2014;161:F77–82. <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.050401jes>.
- [12] Sui S, Ma L, Zhai Y. TiC supported Pt-Ir electrocatalyst prepared by a plasma process for the oxygen electrode in unitized regenerative fuel cells. *J Power Sources* 2011;196:5416–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2011.02.058>.
- [13] Kúš P, Ostroverkh A, Ševčíková K. Magnetron sputtered Ir thin film on TiC-based support sublayer as low-loading anode catalyst for proton exchange membrane water electrolysis. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2016;41:15124–32.
- [14] Li G, Li K, Yang L, Chang J, Ma R, Wu Z, et al. Boosted Performance of Ir Species by Employing TiN as the Support toward Oxygen Evolution Reaction 2018;18. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b14172>.
- [15] Zhang K, Mai W, Li J, Wang H, Li G, Hu W. Highly scattered Ir oxides on TiN as an efficient oxygen evolution reaction electrocatalyst in acidic media. *J Mater Sci* 2020;55:3507–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-019-04201-4>.
- [16] Han X, Mou T, Islam A, Kang S, Chang Q, Xie Z, et al. Theoretical prediction and experimental verification of IrO_x supported on titanium nitride for acidic oxygen evolution reaction. *J Am Chem Soc* 2024;146:16499–510. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.4c02936>.
- [17] Karade SS, Sharma R, Gyergyek S, Morgen P, Andersen SM. IrO₂/Ir composite nanoparticles (IrO₂@Ir) supported on TiN_xO_y coated TiN: efficient and robust oxygen evolution reaction catalyst for water electrolysis. *ChemCatChem* 2023;15. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cctc.202201470>.
- [18] Bele M, Stojanovski K, Jovanovič P, Moriau L, Koderman Podboršek G, Moškon J, et al. Towards stable and conductive titanium oxynitride high-surface-area support for iridium nanoparticles as oxygen evolution reaction electrocatalyst. *ChemCatChem* 2019;11:5038–44. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cctc.201901487>.
- [19] Bizzotto F, Quinson J, Zana A, Kirkensgaard JJK, Dworzak A, Oezaslan M, et al. Ir nanoparticles with ultrahigh dispersion as oxygen evolution reaction (OER) catalysts: Synthesis and activity benchmarking. *Catal Sci Technol* 2019;9:6345–56. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9cy01728c>.